

Communication 22 : BRAND HATE: Types And Antecedents

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ABSTRACT

Purpose-

The purpose of this paper is to test the impact of negative past experience, symbolic incongruity, ideological incompatibility, and subjective norm on different types of brand hate.

Design/Methodology/approach-

We adopted a hypothetico-deductive approach for this research. An online questionnaire was distributed to Moroccan consumers. Results of 266 completed questionnaires were analyzed using PLS-SEM.

Findings–

Significant and positive relationships were found between all antecedents and all types of brand hate.

Originality/value-

To our knowledge, this paper is the first of its kind to test the antecedents of seven types of brand hate separately. It's also the first paper to study brand hate in Morocco and to test its antecedents using a quantitative approach in the Mena region. This study contributes to the literature by providing a framework of internal

factors (negative past experience, symbolic incongruity, and ideological incompatibility) and external factors (subjective norm).

Keywords- :

Brand hate; Consumer psychology; Branding; Consumer-brand relationship; Consumer negativity

